

Special Relativity as a Thermodynamical Type of Theory?

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Statistical systems are complicated, but thermodynamics seeks to describe them in terms of a few average parameters such as energy, pressure, volume, temperature, entropy etc. Force interactions are also complicated, we argue, but Newton was able to formulate a theory using a few variables such as energy, momentum, force, v (velocity), x and t . We try to argue that the Newtonian theory, generalized using special relativity, behaves like a thermodynamic theory. In other words, the parameters p, E, x, t, v are like thermodynamic average values and one may expect more complicated features than what is described by relationships between the variables p, E, x, t due to fluctuations.

We begin with the relativistic expression $E^2 = p^2 c^2 + m_0^2 c^4$ and argue that using $v = dx/dt$, one obtains $-E dt + p dx = -m_0 \sqrt{1-v^2} dt$ ((1)). For $v = dx/dt$ everything is deterministic, but if one considers fluctuations of dx and dt , which break $v = dx/dt$, there are periodic fluctuation solutions to ((1)), namely $t = t_1 + \text{constant}/E$ and $x = x_1 + \text{constant}/p$. We ask: Why should one even consider such fluctuations when they break the condition $v = dx/dt$ and determinism as well? If one considers the parameters E, p, x, t to be like thermodynamic averages underlying a more complicated theory, these fluctuation solutions are not necessarily unusual. For example, a photon satisfies ((1)) with $m_0 = 0$, but a more complicated underlying theory is given by Maxwell's electromagnetic theory, which is consistent with special relativity i.e. with the relationship between thermodynamic-like average quantities.

In general, relationships between the thermodynamic-like variables E, p, x, t, v describe much physics. Is there any experimental reason to consider fluctuation type solutions inherent in ((1))? We argue that the one dimensional reflection-refraction of photons provides concrete experimental evidence that simply using the variable E, p, x, t, v is not sufficient. In other words, there exists an experimental example which lies outside deterministic classical mechanics. In particular, it is the probabilistic nature of the reflection-refraction problem ($\text{Prob}(\text{reflect}) + \text{Prob}(\text{refract}) = 1$) which undermines deterministic classical mechanics. The fluctuation solution of ((1)) is consistent with a complex probability function (probability) $\exp(-iEt + ipx)$ which allows one to calculate $\text{Prob}(\text{reflect})$ and $\text{Prob}(\text{refract})$.

We argue that some deterministic solutions, such as a classical bound system confined within turning points, may be approximations of a more complicated statistical equilibrium scenario involving a bound particle which has probability to leak out of the classical turning points and also reenter. This, in fact, seems to be the quantum mechanical bound state.

Classical Mechanics and Thermodynamics

Classical mechanics was developed to deterministically describe motion. It uses variables such as E, p, x, t, v , Force etc. and is not really associated with probabilities and averages. These ideas were incorporated to deal with large numbers of classical particles, as in a gas, to describe it by a few variables such as E_{average} , volume, pressure, temperature, entropy etc.

One may then write expressions relating these average values instead of dealing with equations describing the microscopic physics. This does not mean that microscopic physics disappears or has no impact. There are fluctuations about averages which show additional physics exists.

We suggest that the parameters E, p, x, t, v , force etc in classical mechanics may also represent thermodynamic-like averages. Classical objects are complicated (they consist of many atoms and have a temperature indicating further motion). Furthermore the details of force may be much more complicated than a description given by $-dV(x)/dx$, where $V(x)$ is a potential. The thermodynamical-like parameters E, p, x, t etc, however, describe a large amount of physics and so the role of fluctuations may be forgotten. We argue, however, that there is experimental evidence for the importance of such fluctuations in certain problems.

Reflection-Refraction of Light

A photon moving in the x direction and reflecting-refracting at an n_1-n_2 (index of refraction interface) along y at x_0 has two probabilities: $\text{Prob}(\text{reflect})$ and $\text{Prob}(\text{refract})$. This problem may be solved using the form $\exp(ipx)$ associated with $\cos(px)$ describing the electric field of a photon. This solution follows from Maxwell's electrodynamic equations. Thus, this problem and its solution seem to follow from what is considered to be classical physics. One simply considers that a photon must satisfy Maxwell's equations which are more complicated than considering E and p for a photon. E and p , nevertheless exist for a photon and Maxwell's theory represents a fuller picture of what occurs.

A second example, which exists in nature is that of tunneling of a particle with rest mass. In such a case, there is no Maxwell's theory to turn to describe this break with classical physics.

We ask: Is it possible to see the existence of more complicated physics (statistical fluctuations) from relationships between thermodynamic-like variables such as E, p, x and t ?

$E^2 = p^2 + m^2$

Special relativity generalizes the results of Newton, but may be obtained by consider the behaviour of the variables E, p, x and t as viewed from different frames moving at constant $-v$. In other words, one assumes a mass (which is a complicated object) at rest at $x=0$ at time t and asks: How does this appear in a frame moving at constant $-v$? The particle appears to move and so one has the rest mass (perhaps enhanced by the motion), but also the notion of pressure, because a moving particle may strike an object. It has a flux proportional to v . In order for the particle to represent a pressure, it must have a force field which may be complicated. Setting this field in motion also involves complications. One may, however, obtain a simple transformation for the variables E, p, x, t using v i.e. Lorentz's transformation:

$$\begin{pmatrix} 1/\sqrt{1-v^2/c^2} & v/\sqrt{1-v^2/c^2} \\ -v/\sqrt{1-v^2/c^2} & 1/\sqrt{1-v^2/c^2} \end{pmatrix} \quad ((2))$$

This leads to two Lorentz invariants: $-Et+px$ ((3a)) and $-E^2+p^2 = -m^2$ ($c=1$). ((3b)).

From these, one may find that $E = m_0 c^2 / \sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2}$ and $pc = Ev$. In the nonrelativistic limit, one obtains $E = p^2/2m_0$ and $p = m_0 v$. In other words, a complicated system of atoms at a temperature may be approximated by an E and p of the center of mass together with x and t . ((3b)) describes the relationship between E , p and m_0 and it seems one has determinism.

We suggest examining ((3b)) more closely.

$$-E + pc = -m_0 c^2 \rightarrow E = p^2/E + m_0^2 c^2/E \rightarrow E = pv + m_0 (m_0 c^2/E) \quad (c=1)$$

$$-m_0 \sqrt{1 - v^2} dt = -E dt + p dx \quad ((4)) \quad \text{where } \sqrt{1 - v^2} dt = dt \text{ rest frame and } v = dx/dt$$

One may see that by breaking the constraint $v = dx/dt$, one may have fluctuations in dx and dt which leave ((4)) unchanged in particular:

$$dt \rightarrow dt + \delta t \text{ constant}/E \text{ and } dx \rightarrow dx + \delta x \text{ constant}/p \quad ((5))$$

Similar conclusions follow from considering $-E + pc$, but by using $-E + pc = -m_0 c^2$, one explicitly obtains dx and dt values which indicate changes or fluctuations. As a result, periodic fluctuations are included in what seems to be a deterministic equation i.e. ((3b)). In fact, ((3b)) is Newton's conservation of energy equation for a free particle when written in the nonrelativistic limit.

Why should fluctuations appear in what is seemingly a deterministic theory? We argue that matters are much more complicated than what is displayed by ((3b)). ((3b)) includes thermodynamic average-like quantities like E, p, x, t and is a correct description of a relationship between them, but there is more occurring. If extra physics appears in ((3b)), we suggest it should be taken seriously. One, however, requires experimental proof.

This proof comes in the form of the already described photon one dimensional reflection-refraction problem. One needs to find $P(\text{reflect})$, $P(\text{refract})$ and deterministic classical mechanics does not yield these probabilities. A complex probability $\exp(-iEt + ipx)$ based on the fluctuations described above, however, does. One may note that ((3b)) with $m_0 = 0$ yield $E = pc$. If E remains constant, then p and c may change to accommodate this. If one has an $n_1 - n_2$ interface for which there is only refraction, there is no question of probability. If, however, reflection and refraction occur, one has a probabilistic situation which is outside the realm of classical determinism. The classical type equation $E = pc$, however, includes a description of fluctuations needed to solve the problem i.e.

$$E = pc \rightarrow -E dt + p dx = 0 \quad ((6))$$

This suggests again the fluctuations of ((5)). For the reflection-refraction problem one uses continuity of a fluctuation probability and its first derivative at x_0 i.e.

$$A \exp(ipx) + B \exp(-ipx) = C \exp(ip_2 x) \text{ and } A p \exp(ipx) - B p \exp(-ipx) = C p_2 \exp(ip_2 x) \text{ both at } x_0 \quad ((7))$$

As a result, one has a problem which requires fluctuations, which appear in $E^2 = p^2 + m^2 c^4$, for its solution. One must go beyond classical determinism and include what one calls quantum mechanics.

This quantum picture goes beyond classical mechanics in another way, namely in the description of a bound state. Classically, a bound particle moves between two sharp classical turning points. We have argued, however, that E, p, x and t are thermodynamic-like average values and may take on sharp values. Physically, however, things may not be so sharp. Using $\exp(-ipx)$ to create an average kinetic energy = $\{ \text{Sum over } p \ a(p) p^2 / 2m \exp(ipx) \} / \{ \text{Sum over } p \ a(p) \exp(ipx) \}$ which when added to $V(x)$ (potential) yields E_n at all x points, yields a solution for $\text{Sum over } p \ a(p) \exp(ipx)$ at all x points, not just within classical turning points. We suggest that this is a statistical equilibrium type picture which results based on the fluctuations contained in $-E^2 + p^2 = m^2 c^4$ ($c=1$).

Conclusion

Classical mechanics makes use of variables such as $E, p, x, t, v, \text{Force}$ to create a deterministic picture of dynamics. We suggest, however, classical objects are complicated combinations of atoms at a certain temperature and that complicated force fields are also involved. We suggest that E, p, x, t etc are thermodynamic-like average variables whose interrelationships may describe some average properties of such systems, but not everything. For example, there may be statistical fluctuations if the thermodynamic-like assumption is correct. Where are these fluctuations? We suggest they appear in the relativistic Lorentz invariants $-E^2 + p^2 = m^2 c^4$ ($c=1$) and $-Et = px$. Here we focus on the former which yields $-E dt + p dx = -m_0 dt \sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2}$. The equation is written in terms of dt and dx , i.e. changes, with $dx/dt = v$. If one breaks this average condition, i.e. includes fluctuations, one notices there are periodic fluctuations of the form ((5)) which are consistent with a complex probability of $\exp(-iEt + ipx)$. We suggest that experimental proof for such fluctuations appears in the one dimensional photon reflection-refraction problem. This problem introduces probabilities which immediately break with classical determinism. One may argue that this problem may be solved using the photonic electric field from Maxwell's equation, but $E = pc$ is consistent with Maxwell's photon and includes the fluctuations which solve the problem.. $E = pc$, however, is a relationship between thermodynamic-like variables, with Maxwell's equations being an underlying more complicated theory. If one uses $\exp(ipx)$'s in a system with a potential $V(x)$, one obtains a statistical solution which allows for tunneling and out of the bound system's classical turning points. This again goes beyond classical determinism.